

LATTICE TRUSS CORE SANDWICH STRUCTURES WITH AL LATTICE TRUSS CORE AND CFRP COMPOSITE FACHESHEETS UNDER IMPACT LOADS

WANG Bing¹, Zhu Shaowei¹ and Zhang Guoqi²

¹Center for Composite Materials and Structures, Harbin Institute of Technology,
Harbin 150001, P.R. China

Email: wangbing86@hit.edu.cn, web page: <http://homepage.hit.edu.cn/pages/wangbing>

²Beijing spacecrafts, Beijing 100190, P.R.China

Email: zhangflag04@163.com

Keywords: Lattice truss core, Sandwich structure, Energy absorption, Low velocity impact

ABSTRACT

In this paper, the pyramidal truss core sandwich structures consisting of carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) facesheets and aluminum alloy lattice truss cores were manufactured based on the slot-fitting method. This hybrid concept is to maximize the specific bending stiffness/strength as well as obtain excellent energy absorption ability. Low velocity impact tests were carried out to evaluate the energy absorption mechanism and the damage resistance. The experimental results show that the low density Al alloy lattice truss core have superior energy absorption ability compared with other lightweight lattice cores. In the low velocity impact tests, the main failure modes are the failure of matrix cracking, fiber breakage, delamination of CFRP facesheets and buckling of truss members occurred. In addition to experimental testing, finite element models for compression and impact simulations have been developed using ABAQUS software. Despite the high degree of complexity of the models due to the various skin and core failure modes that have to be covered, the results correlate well with test data, allowing for efficient parameter studies or detailed evaluations of damage patterns and energy absorption mechanisms.

1 INTRODUCTION

Sandwich structures are widely used in lightweight construction especially in aerospace industries because of their high specific strength and stiffness. Unlike metallic foams with stochastic open or closed cell structures [1], lattice core sandwich structures have uniform-structures that are based on repeating unit cells. Applications of lattice core sandwich structures range from ultra-light weight multifunctional structures to automobile, aerospace components, furniture and sporting goods [2]. The interest in such applications has stimulated recent efforts to develop new fabrication methods [3 - 6] and significant efforts have also been made to model and characterize the basic mechanical properties [7 - 10]of lattice core sandwich structures.

Although CFRP truss cores have higher specific stiffness and strength over metal lattice truss cores, their energy absorption was poor due to the premature brittle rupture or delamination of truss members [11-14]. In addition, the shaping of composite truss core topologies was rather complex compared with metal truss cores. In order to tackle some of the existing weakness of the lattice truss core sandwich structure, a hybrid sandwich structure has been developed by combining the advantages of CFRP and metal while avoiding some of their major disadvantages. The design concept is using CFRP laminate as the facesheets to maximize the specific bending stiffness/strength while introducing lightweight metal cores to obtain excellent energy absorption ability.

To date, a great deal of research work has been carried out in investigating the residual compressive strength of foam/honeycomb core sandwich structures subjected to low velocity impact.

However, according to the authors' knowledge, only a few works are devoted to the impact behavior of lattice truss core sandwich structures and. Thus, the aim of this paper is to study the residual compressive strength of impact-damaged pyramidal truss core sandwich structures. The present study is carried out over a range of impact energy, core density and impact site to discuss the effects of factors mentioned above on the impact damage. The impact tests are analyzed in terms of the load histories and failure modes. According, the content of this paper is structured as follows. Firstly, we investigate the impact response of sandwich structures with pyramidal truss cores under the low velocity impact.

2 EXPERIMENTS

2.1 MATERIALS

The pyramidal truss core sandwich structures are fabricated and the details of the process have been introduced in our previous work[15]. The pyramidal lattice truss core were made from aluminum alloy sheets(2A12-T4). The facesheets were made of carbon fiber/epoxy composites (T700/3234). Fig 1a gives a typical pyramidal truss core sandwich panel. The unit cell geometry of pyramidal truss core is shown in Fig.1b. The corresponding parameters of core investigated in this paper are listed in table 1. The relative density $\bar{\rho}$ of the pyramidal truss core is written as follows:

$$\bar{\rho} = \frac{4btl + 4[(h_a + h_b)ct - ch_a]}{ha^2} \quad (1)$$

Fig.1.(a):Composite pyramidal truss core sandwich panel. (b):The unit cell geometry of the pyramidal lattice core.

Table1 The pyramidal lattice core parameter (mm)

ω	h	t	b	c	h_a	h_b	l	$\bar{\rho}$
45°	15	1.4	1.5	8	1.5	1.5	14.85	2.58%

2.2 Low velocity impact tests

The Instron Dynatup 9250HV impact testing machine is used for the low velocity impact tests. During tests, the impactor possesses a hemispherical nose of 12.1mm in diameter and a force transducer is mounted in the hemispherical impactor nose with the capacity of 22KN. The specimens are fixed by the pneumatic clamps, with a 76.2mm diameter opening, which secure specimens during impact tests. The

clamping pressure of 0.02MPa is imposed on the pneumatic clamps, which is well below the lowest compressive strength of the lattice cores. During tests, the varied impact energies are achieved by changing the drop height and the impactor mass is assigned 6.15kg for all tests in the present study. The impact response of the specimens including velocity, displacement, load and energy are recorded and stored by computer using data acquisition software.

To explore the effects of impact site on the damage, two representative impact sites are chosen in the present study. One case is the impact site located on the node (impact site SN) and the other impact site is the middle point of the four adjacent nodes (impact site SM), as shown in Fig.2. The impact load versus contact time curves of the specimens associated with the impact damage are plotted in Fig.3.

Fig. 2. The impact location during tests. (a) Impact location on the node and (b) impact location on the middle point of four adjacent nodes.

Fig.3. Impact load versus contact time curves and the impact damage

For the lower impact energy (5J), the smoother impact load curves mean that there is slight damage in the specimen, as shown in Fig.3a. It is found that there is matrix cracking emerges along the orientation perpendicular to the fiber for the specimens. Moreover, delamination is very obvious at the distal surface of top facesheet around the impact region, while the truss members under the impactor suffer buckling. The sharp load drop in Fig.8e indicates that there is considerable damage for the specimen impacted on the middle point of the four adjacent nodes, which is confirmed from the penetration of the top facesheet. This can be explained that a lot of impact energy is absorbed by the truss members under the impactor and the truss members can give additional support to the impactor when the impact location is on the node. In contrast, there is no extra support for impactor when the middle point of the four adjacent is impacted. At 8J, a series of oscillations in the impact load curve is found, as shown in Fig.8b. Examination reveals that the indentation is quite visible at the impact location with fiber breakage on the top facesheet. From Fig.8c, it is quite noticeable that a sharp load drop occurs in the test. This load drop is due to the penetration of the facesheet at the impact region and fracture of truss members. At the impact energy of 30J, it is evident that the impact load-time curves are of a mountain-like shape with two peaks as shown in Fig.8d, implying the contact of impactor with the top and bottom facesheets, respectively.

3 SIMULATION

The explicit finite element software, ABAQUS/Explicit, is employed for impact simulation. The sandwich plate is modeled as a rectangular plate, and clamped at its top and bottom circumferential edges to simulate the clamped condition in test machine, as shown in Fig. 4. The rectangular specimen is chosen for the test of residual tensile strength in the next section. Since the integrative forming method is employed to manufacture this new sandwich structure [11], interfaces between facesheets and lattice core are undamaged under impact and tension process. So, fiber columns core is assumed to be perfectly bonding with facesheets in FE model. The facesheets are meshed with linear reduced integration solid elements, with each ply in the laminate represented by a solid element in the through-thickness direction. The fiber columns core is also meshed with linear reduced integration solid elements. Due to the poor aspect ratio of these elements, a reasonably fine mesh is required to ensure convergence. A graded mesh is thus created, where the region in the vicinity of the impactor is more finely meshed. Convergence study of FE results is conducted to ensure that the mesh refinement in the sandwich structure is sufficiently fine enough to capture the stresses and deformations with reasonable accuracy. Surface-based tie constraints are implemented on the interfaces between facesheets and core, which are assumed to be perfectly bonded. Finally, the semi-spherical steel indenter with diameter 12.7 mm is modeled as a rigid body using a rigid body constraint. It is meshed with 4-noded linear tetrahedron continuum elements with Young's modulus 200 GPa and Poisson's ratio 0.3.

The property parameters of the CFRP facesheet and aluminum alloy as well as their stress-strain behavior after the damage initiation are detailed in [28]. Surface-based cohesive behavior is defined to model the debonding between the core and facesheets in this model [30]. The damage initiation is based on the quadratic separation criterion, which is expressed as follows:

$$\left\{ \frac{\langle \delta_n \rangle}{\delta_n^0} \right\}^2 + \left\{ \frac{\delta_s}{\delta_s^0} \right\}^2 + \left\{ \frac{\delta_t}{\delta_t^0} \right\}^2 = 1 \quad (2)$$

where δ_n , δ_s and δ_t are the current separations along the contact normal and purely in the first and the second shear direction, respectively. δ_n^0 , δ_s^0 , and δ_t^0 represent the peak displacement values of the contact separation, when the separation is either purely along the contact normal and purely in the first and the second shear direction, respectively. The symbol $\langle \rangle$ used in Eq.(2) represents the Macaulay bracket with the usual interpretation.

The damage evolution for the cohesive surface is defined based on the energy conjunction with the exponential softening law. This criterion can be represented as:

$$\left\{ \frac{G_n}{G_n^C} \right\}^\alpha + \left\{ \frac{G_s}{G_s^C} \right\}^\alpha + \left\{ \frac{G_t}{G_t^C} \right\}^\alpha = 1 \quad (3)$$

where G_n , G_s and G_t refer to the work done by the traction and its conjugate separation in the normal, the first, and the second shear directions; G_n^C , G_s^C and G_t^C refer to the critical fracture energies required to cause failure in the normal, the first, and the second shear directions, respectively. While α is a non-dimensional parameter that defines the rate of damage evolution. In the above expressions, Eq.(2) and (3), the corresponding parameters are given in Table 2.

Table 2 The parameters used in the cohesive behavior

δ_n^0 (m)	δ_s^0 (m)	δ_t^0 (m)	G_n^C (J/m ²)	G_s^C (J/m ²)	G_t^C (J/m ²)	α
1.0×10^{-7}	1.5×10^{-7}	1.5×10^{-7}	2000	3000	3000	2.0

Further details of the finite element model for the sandwich structure such as the element, contact and constraint can be found in [28], and the finite element model is plotted in Fig.4.

These comparisons indicate that there is a good agreement between the experimental and predicted results in terms of time duration, peak force and overall profile. The predicted impact damage of specimen SN-5J is depicted in Fig.5, while the damage of each ply of facesheet is superimposed. The predicted damage is represented in rainbow color; red regions indicate that the material has failed

completely while in lighter gray areas the material comes closer to failure; white regions indicate that the elements have been removed for distorted deformation while in blue areas the material is normal. The damage consists of fiber damage, matrix damage and delamination as well as the buckling of truss members, which agree well with the experiments.

Fig.4. The finite element model

Fig.5. Numerically predicted impact damage for specimen SN-5J.(a) The fiber tensile failure on the top facesheet; (b) The fiber compressive failure on the top facesheet; (c) The matrix tensile failure on the top facesheet; (d) The matrix compressive failure on the top facesheet;(e) The delamination failure on the top facesheet; (f) The truss core failure

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a combined experimental and numerical study for low velocity impact response of sandwich structures consisting of CFRP facesheets and aluminum alloy pyramidal truss core is presented. Impact tests are conducted in a drop weight tower over a range of energies. The low

velocity impact tests reveal that the extent of damage is significantly affected by the impact site. When the impact site is the node, the peak force ascends with core relative density increasing and the contact time prolongs with the impact energy increasing. The failure in the impact tests is dominated by the matrix cracking and the buckling of truss members under the impactor. Once the impact energy increases, the recorded impact force shows a sudden drop from the peak point. Moreover, it is found that the extent of damage is significantly affected by the impact site. The samples suffered more serious damage when the impact sites were among the nodes. Also, the numerical simulation based on ABAQUS was conducted. The numerical results agree fairly well with the experiments especially for the lower impact energy case. This has particular importance for the designer to understand the mechanism involved in the low velocity impact event, prior to conducting tests, and therefore to design impact-resistant lightweight structures.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The present work is supported by the Major State Basic Research Development Program of China (973 Program) under Grant No. 2011CB610303, and the National Science Foundation of China under Grant Nos. 11202059,

REFERENCES

- [1] Gibson LJ, Ashby MF. Cellular solids: structure and properties. 2nded. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press; 2000.
- [2] Jamcorp. <<http://www.jamcorp.com/brochure/brochure.htm>>.
- [3] Evans AG, Hutchinson JW, Fleck NA, Ashby MF, Wadley HNG. The topology design of multifunctional cellular metals. *Prog Mater Sci* 2001;46:309–27.
- [4] Evans AG. Lightweight materials and structures. *MRS Bull* 2001;26:790–7.
- [5] Brittain ST, Sugimura Y, Schueller OJA, Evans AG, Whitesides GM. Fabrication and mechanical performance of a mesoscale space-filling truss system. *J Microelectromech Syst* 2001;10:113–20.
- [6] Krause DL, Whittenberger JD, Kantzos PT, Hebsur MG. Mechanical testing of IN718 lattice block structures. In: *Processing and properties of lightweight cellular metals and structures. Proceedings of TMS, Seattle; 2002.* p. 233–42.
- [7] Deshpande VS, Fleck NA, Ashby MF. Effective properties of the octet-truss lattice material. *J Mech Phys Solids* 2001;49:1747–69
- [8] Deshpande VS, Fleck NA, Ashby MF. Collapse of truss core sandwich beams in 3-point bending. *Int J Solids Struct* 2001;38:6275–305.
- [9] Wallach JC, Gibson LJ. Mechanical behavior of a three-dimensional truss material. *Int J Solids Struct* 2001;38:7181–96.
- [10] Wallach JC, Gibson LJ. Defect sensitivity of a 3D truss material. *Scripta Mater* 2001;45:639–44.
- [11] Finnegan K, Kooistra G, Wadley Haydn NG, Deshpande VS. The compressive response of carbon fiber composite pyramidal truss sandwich cores. *Int J Mater Res* 2007;98:1264–72.
- [12] Fan Hualin, Yang Wei, Zhou Qing. Experimental research of compressive responses of multi-layered woven textile sandwich panels under quasi-static loading. *Composites Part B* 2011;42:1151–6.
- [13] Wang Bing, Linzhi Wu, Ma Li. Mechanical behavior of the sandwich structures with carbon fiber-reinforced pyramidal lattice truss core. *Mater Des* 2010;31:2659–63.
- [14] Xiong Jian, Ma Li, Linzhi Wu, Wang Bing. Fabrication and crushing behavior of low density carbon fiber composite pyramidal truss structures. *Compos Struct* 2010;92:2695–702.
- [15] Guoqi Zhang, Bing Wang, Li Ma, Jian Xiong, Linzhi Wu. Response of sandwich structures with pyramidal truss cores under the compression and impact loading. *Compos Struct*.2013,100:451-463